

and fertilizer were followed. Rice yield, weed species, and weed weights were determined at harvest.

Results are shown in the table. Whether direct-seeded or transplanted, the high yielding variety BR3 outyielded the local variety. When transplanted, it produced 31% more yield than when direct-seeded. The local variety had lower yields because of its low tillering rate when transplanted; however, it yielded 40% more when direct-seeded.

Weeds were a problem in the direct-seeded plots. The control plot had significantly lower yields, 39% less than the herbicide-treated and hand-weeded

plots.

The best treatment combined a low dose of herbicide and hand weeding. Although the yield it gave did not differ significantly from that of hand weeding, it was better than that of any of the three herbicide treatments. In Bangladesh, the combination of a low dose of herbicide and weeding would be practical and would complement the existing hand-weeding methods.

The transplanted plot had less weed infestation and showed no significant reduction in yield between the control and the herbicide-alone plots. A low dose of herbicide plus hand weeding, however,

increased yields by 9% over the control. The cultural practice of puddling plus the competitive advantage of the transplanted rice plant over weeds greatly reduced weed problems where water management was good.

The weed species present in the BR3 and Dharial plots differed. In BR3 the sedges *Cyperus iria*, *Cyperus difformis*, and *Fimbristylis littoralis* were the major weeds. In the plots of the taller Dharial, sedge growth was much reduced, and the grass *Echinochloa crus-galli* was the dominant weed. Weed weights in the Dharial direct-seeded control plots were 92 g/m² compared with 133 g/m² in BR3.

Soil and crop management

Residual effect of blue-green algae application on rice yield

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Field trials to determine the residual effect of blue-green algae for nitrogen fixation on rice yields were laid out using ADT31 during the 1975 and 1976 kar (July–Oct.) season and using IR20 during the 1975 and 1976 pishanam (Nov.–March) season. The treatments were 50–25–25 kg NPK/ha, 50–25–25 kg NPK/ha plus 10 kg algae/ha, 25–25–25 kg NPK/ha, 25–25–25 kg/ha plus 10 kg algae/ha, algae alone at 10 kg/ha, and the untreated control.

After four seasons, the same treatments were repeated during the 1977 kar and 1977–78 pishanam seasons, with no algae added. Withholding algae did not generally affect the yield trend much (see table). In the plots where algae alone were applied, however, yields decreased slightly in the 1977 kar season. The results indicate that the residual effects of application of blue-green algae for a continuous period of four seasons will provide sufficient inoculum for subsequent crops.

Effect of blue-green algae on rice yields, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	1977 kar season ^a		1977–78 pishanam season ^b	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase or decrease over control (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase or decrease over control (%)
0 NPK	3.3	–	4.8	–
0 NPK + blue-green algae	3.2	3.2	5.4	13.9
25–25–25 kg NPK/ha	3.3	2.2	5.2	7.6
25–25–25 kg NPK/ha + blue-green algae	3.8	17.1	5.2	9.8
50–25–25 kg NPK/ha	3.8	11.2	5.1	7.6
50–25–25 kg NPK/ha + 10 kg/ha blue-green algae	4.1	24.6	5.1	7.6
F test:	S		NS	
CD:	456		–	

^aJuly–October. ^bNovember–March.

Fertilizers for deep placement and slow release of nitrogen for rice

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Rice commonly uses only 30 to 40% of applied fertilizer nitrogen. A great deal of research has therefore been carried out to develop more efficient nitrogen fertilizer sources and management

practices.

Three major approaches that have been developed are split application, deep placement, and controlled release. The latter two approaches — as mudballs or urea supergranules and sulfur-coated urea, respectively — have frequently proven superior to split application of urea in experiments conducted in the 10 countries of the International Network on Fertilizer Efficiency in Rice.

A fourth approach combines the deep placement and slow-release concepts. A